

1 **Modeling platform to assess the effectiveness of single and**
2 **integrated *Ixodes scapularis* tick control methods**

3 Daniel Ruiz-Carrascal^{1,2}, Jonathan Bastard¹, Scott C. Williams³, and Maria Diuk-Wasser^{1,*}

4
5 ¹ *Department of Ecology, Evolution and Environmental Biology, Columbia University in the City*
6 *of New York, New York, United States*

7 ² *International Research Institute for Climate and Society, Columbia University in the City of New*
8 *York, New York, United States*

9 ³ *Department of Environmental Science and Forestry, Center for Vector Biology & Zoonotic*
10 *Diseases, The Connecticut Agricultural Experiment Station, New Haven, Connecticut, United*
11 *States*

12 * Corresponding author: mad2256@columbia.edu ; 1200 Amsterdam Avenue, 10th Fl.
13 Schermerhorn Ext., New York, NY 10027.

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17 None to declare.

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Abstract

25 Lyme disease continues to expand in Canada and the United States and no single intervention is
26 likely to curb the epidemic. We propose a platform to quantitatively assess the effectiveness of
27 different *Ixodes scapularis* tick management approaches. The platform allows us to assess the
28 impact of different control treatments, which are either conducted individually (single
29 interventions) or in combination (combined efforts), with different timings and durations.
30 Interventions include three low environmental toxicity measures in differing combinations,
31 namely reductions in white-tailed deer (*Odocoileus virginianus*) population, broadcast area-
32 application of the entomopathogenic fungus *Metarhizium anisopliae*, and fipronil-based rodent-
33 targeted bait boxes. To assess the impact of these control efforts, we calibrated a process-based
34 mathematical model to data collected from residential properties in the town of Redding,
35 southwestern Connecticut, where an integrated tick management program to reduce *Ixodes*
36 *scapularis* nymphs was conducted from 2013 through 2016. We estimated parameters
37 mechanistically related to each of the three treatments, simulated multiple combinations and
38 timings of interventions, and computed the resulting percent reduction of the nymphal peak and of
39 the area under the phenology curve. Simulation outputs suggest that the three-treatment
40 combination and the bait boxes-deer reduction combination had the overall highest impacts on
41 suppressing *Ixodes scapularis* nymphs. All (single or combined) interventions were more
42 efficacious when implemented for a higher number of years. When implemented for at least four
43 years, most interventions (except the single application of the entomopathogenic fungus) were
44 predicted to strongly reduce the nymphal peak compared to the “no intervention” scenario. Finally,
45 we determined the optimal period to apply the entomopathogenic fungus in residential yards,
46 depending on the number of applications. Computer simulation is a powerful tool to identify the
47 optimal deployment of individual and combined tick management approaches, which can
48 synergistically contribute to short- to long-term, cost-effective and sustainable control of tick-
49 borne diseases in integrated tick management (ITM) interventions.

50 Keywords: *Lyme disease, tick control, interventions, effectiveness, simulation, mathematical*
51 *model*

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Introduction

54 Tick-borne diseases are expanding globally¹⁻³. In Canada and the United States, the number of
55 cases of one of these zoonotic diseases, Lyme disease, is on a steady rise⁴⁻⁸. This long-term trend
56 has been attributed to the range expansion of the primary vector to humans, the blacklegged tick,
57 *Ixodes scapularis* Say⁹⁻¹¹. Complementary approaches have been developed to reduce human
58 exposure to the causative agent of Lyme disease, *Borrelia burgdorferi*. One group of interventions
59 targets reduction in the density of ticks in the environment, another aims to decrease the infection
60 prevalence of ticks, and the other aims to reduce human-tick encounters. We will focus here on
61 methods suppressing *Ixodes scapularis* abundance in the environment, which include area-wide
62 application of natural and synthetic acaricidal compounds, landscape and vegetative cover
63 modifications and management¹², host-targeted synthetic acaricides such as fipronil-based rodent-
64 targeted bait boxes¹³⁻¹⁵, biological control¹⁶ by entomopathogenic fungal agents¹⁷⁻¹⁹ and
65 reductions of white-tailed deer, *Odocoileus virginianus*, populations^{20,21}.

66 Integrated Tick Management (ITM) has been proposed to be more effective than single measures
67^{22,23}. However, there is limited empirical support²⁴⁻²⁸ and gaps of knowledge on the effectiveness
68 of such integrated tick control methods still remain^{17,29}. A significant barrier in the evaluation and
69 optimization of ITM approaches is that the outcome of the intervention is often assessed as the
70 reduction in the density of nymphs/infected nymphs, but there is a lack of mechanistic
71 understanding about what component of the enzootic cycle was impacted. For example, when
72 assessing the effect of white-tailed deer (*Odocoileus virginianus*) reduction, the direct effect in
73 reducing deer number is not assessed, rather the focus is on changes in the entomological
74 inoculation rate (measured as the density of host-seeking *Ixodes scapularis* nymphs infected with
75 the target pathogen), the metric of human health risk. While useful in assessing effectiveness of
76 the intervention in reducing human risk in the particular context assessed, this ‘black-box’
77 evaluation limits our ability to expand the application to other settings or optimizing different arms
78 of an ITM approach.

79 We here present a robust, empirically calibrated modeling platform that can simulate and compare
80 single and combined interventions, including differences in timing of delivery. Mathematical
81 modeling approaches provide a mechanistic understanding of the tick-hosts system. They also
82 represent the system’s continuous (i.e., not restricted to specific periods) time dynamics in

83 simulations, and thus capture the temporal complexity of intervention implementation. Using an
84 adaptation of an extensively-validated climate-driven model^{30,31}, we propose a modeling platform
85 to evaluate the impact of individual and multiple tick management approaches on the density of
86 *Ixodes scapularis* nymphs, a key component of Lyme disease risk³².

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Methods

89 *General approach.* The platform integrates a process-based mechanistic model with local weather
90 forcing and set of interventions (Figure 1). We calibrated the mechanistic model using data from
91 previously published studies by our group^{27,28} involving residential yards that underwent single
92 or combined tick-reduction interventions, or were included as reference (no intervention) houses
93 (see Supplementary Table S1). First, we calibrated the model parameters related to tick phenology
94 (in absence of intervention) to the data from reference properties. Second, using the data from
95 properties where interventions were implemented, we calibrated more specifically three
96 parameters quantifying the temporal effects of these interventions on biological mechanisms.
97 Depending on the duration and intensity of the interventions, we modeled them either as “pulse”
98 (instantaneous perturbation of the system, followed by a gradual return to previous state) or “press”
99 interventions (sustained perturbation of the system at constant intensity)³³. Third, we simulated
100 the fully calibrated model to generate multiple scenarios of interventions (including their timing).
101 Finally, we analyzed the results of these data-informed model predictions to quantitatively
102 compare the efficacy of these different ITM approaches for the reduction in the density of questing
103 nymphs.

104 *Process-based model.* To represent the population dynamics of *Ixodes scapularis* ticks, we
105 implemented an R-version of the Ogden et al.³⁰ process-based, mechanistic model. The tool is
106 based on a system of twelve coupled, nonlinear ordinary differential equations, each representing
107 a given life stage or activity level of the tick population: eggs; hardening, questing, feeding, and
108 engorged larvae; questing, feeding and engorged nymphs; questing adults; and feeding, engorged
109 and egg-laying adult females (see Supplementary Tables S2 to S5). The mathematical tool was
110 modified to include the impact of weather and climate on the mortality (or survival) rate of questing

111 *Ixodes scapularis* nymphs and on the host finding probability, which were both assumed to be
112 constant in the original version.

113 *Integrated vector control data used for calibration.* Data used to calibrate the model were derived
114 from an intervention study previously implemented on residential properties in the town of
115 Redding (41.3044°N, -73.3928°W), Fairfield County, in southwestern Connecticut. Specifically,
116 an ITM program to reduce *Ixodes scapularis* nymphs was conducted from January 2013 through
117 September 2016^{27,28}. During that period, a total number of forty-one (41) properties were selected
118 to run the program, including twelve reference (no intervention) properties and 29 properties with
119 implemented interventions. Interventions included single treatments and two- and three-way
120 combinations of three measures, namely white-tailed deer population reduction (hereafter Deer),
121 broadcast area-application of the entomopathogenic fungus *Metarhizium anisopliae* (Met52), and
122 fipronil-based small rodent bait boxes (FipBox). Bait boxes were deployed twice in each house
123 during the summer season (May to August). The sample sizes for each intervention and
124 combination thereof are described in the Supplementary material (Table S1).

125 *Weather data.* The model was forced with temperature, humidity and day length, the first two
126 variables corrected to reflect environmental conditions under the leaf litter. Linear transformations
127 from air temperature and relative humidity to leaf litter temperature and moisture were determined
128 using data collected at 1-meter above ground surface (HOBO U23-001 Pro v2 dataloggers) and in
129 the leaf litter (iButtons) during sampling seasons between 2013 and 2020. Indeed, *Ixodes*
130 *scapularis* live primarily under leaf litter in forest habitats, where temperature is more moderate
131 than the surrounding air³⁴, and relative humidity is higher and less variable than in the air directly
132 above³⁵. Differences in microclimate at this scale are sufficient to mediate activity between a
133 quiescent state in the leaf litter and questing atop vegetation. To characterize weather conditions,
134 we used three data sources: satellite-gauge combined climatic records, weather observations, and
135 reanalysis data. A full description of weather datasets used in our simulations is provided in the
136 Supplementary Note 1. The adapted Ogden et al.³⁰ mechanistic model implemented here thus
137 includes: temperature-dependent development rates for eggs and engorged larvae, nymphs, and
138 females; temperature- and humidity-dependent survival rates of free-living ticks; temperature-,
139 day length- and host density-dependent host-finding rates; and density-dependent survival of ticks
140 during engorgement.

141 *Host data.* According to the 2013-2016 live trapping campaign ^{27,28}, which yielded a grand total
142 of 1,298 small mammal hosts captured from residential properties, hosts for immature ticks in the
143 area included the white-footed mouse (*Peromyscus leucopus*; 86.4% of all small hosts), the eastern
144 chipmunk (*Tamias striatus*; 9.0%), the eastern meadow vole (*Microtus pennsylvanicus*; 2.2%), the
145 northern short-tailed shrew (*Blarina brevicauda*; 1.9%), the American red squirrel (*Tamiasciurus*
146 *hudsonicus*; 0.2%), and the eastern gray squirrel (*Sciurus carolinensis*; 0.1%). Because white-
147 footed mice dominated the small mammal community, we restricted the hosts for immature ticks
148 to white-footed mice and white-tailed deer was the only host for *I. scapularis* adults in the
149 simulations. In our simulations, host populations were assumed to be constant.

150 *Simulating tick population dynamics.* The model was run for a time horizon spanning from January
151 1, 1950 to December 31, 2020; i.e., 25,933 days. This long-term period considers an initial 10-
152 year burn-in period for the model to reach equilibrium and additional 10 years to assess day-to-
153 day fluctuations of the tick population after the model has reached stable conditions. The remaining
154 50 years of the simulation run include the final 2013-2019 experimentation period, for which data
155 are available on the observed densities of questing *Ixodes scapularis* nymphs, expressed per 100
156 m², from a total of 1,244 tick dragging collections conducted over the research period ^{27,28}.

157 *Calibration of the model's tick phenology parameters.* Parameters related to tick phenology in the
158 mathematical model were first calibrated to questing nymphal data collected at the reference
159 properties (we averaged the observed questing nymphal data of the twelve houses), by
160 simultaneously minimizing three statistical errors: the percent error, BE ³⁶, the root mean square
161 error, RMSE ³⁷, and the general tendency, Pbias ³⁸ and maximizing the Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency,
162 NSE ³⁹.

163 *Efficacy of interventions.* We then used the data collected from the 29 properties where single or
164 combinations of interventions were implemented (see Table S1) to estimate their efficacy. For a
165 given year in a given house, the “Deer” treatment was assumed to multiply the host-finding
166 probability for questing adults (λ_{QA}) between January 1st and December 31st by a factor f_D , where
167 f_D was calibrated to the data (“press” function).

168 We considered that the “Met52” treatment affected the *per capita mortality rate of questing*
169 *nymphs* (μ_{QN}) and *questing adults* (μ_{QA}) of the process-based model as a “pulse” (instantaneous

170 perturbation) function. Immediately after the treatment was applied, these two parameters were
171 increased by a factor f_M (calibrated to the data), followed by a gradual decay in mortality over the
172 effective residual life of Met52, back towards their baseline (without intervention) values at a rate
173 given by:

$$174 \quad 1 + f_M \cdot \max(0; 1 - e^{-\left(\frac{\log(0.1)}{14}\right) \cdot (\Delta t - 28)}) \quad (1)$$

175 where Δt depicts the number of days since the treatment application. The effective residual life of
176 Met52 was assumed to be 4 weeks⁴⁰. The first and second application rounds took place in early
177 June and early July respectively, leading to an impact of Met52 Only treatment lasting for two
178 consecutive months (early June to early August), consistent with the broadcast applications during
179 the 2013-2016 control campaign.

180 Similarly, the “FipBox” treatment was assumed to impact the *per-capita mortality rate of feeding*
181 *larvae* (μ_{FL}) and *feeding nymphs* (μ_{FN}) of the process-based model as a “pulse” function (see Figure
182 S1). These two parameters were increased by a factor f_F (calibrated to the data) after boxes were
183 deployed, followed by a gradual decay in mortality over the effective residual life of the
184 compound, back towards their baseline (without intervention) values at a rate given by:

$$185 \quad 1 + f_F \cdot \max(0; 1 - e^{-\left(\frac{\log(0.1)}{28}\right) \cdot (\Delta t - 56)}) \quad (2)$$

186 where Δt depicts the number of days since the treatment application. The effective residual life of
187 the compound was assumed to be 8 weeks. To account for two deployments of bait boxes during
188 the campaign, we simulated an increase in tick mortality in early May and again after 8 weeks (i.e.,
189 approximately sixteen weeks in total), the period after which bait boxes were retrieved.

190 Parameters f_D , f_M and f_F were simultaneously estimated by minimizing the RMSE for all 29 houses
191 with interventions, allowing to assess the effect of each individual intervention despite their
192 simultaneous implementation in some of the houses.

193 *Simulation of the effectiveness of ITM approaches.* Using the values of f_D , f_M and f_F estimated from
194 the data, we simulated the implementation of all combinations of the three treatments: Deer Only
195 (D), Met52 Only (M), FipBox Only (F), Deer+Met52 (D+M), Deer+FipBox (D+F),
196 Met52+FipBox (M+F) and Deer+Met52+FipBox (D+M+F).

197 *Simulation of alternative number and timing of interventions.* The last set of simulations included
198 the analysis of changes in the “Met52 Only” treatment applications. Starting from the baseline
199 scenario with two applications of the treatment in early June and early July, respectively, we
200 assessed the effects of shifting the timing of application and reducing the number of applications.
201 We simulated a change in the dates of both Met52 applications: the first application taking place
202 between late April and mid-July, and the second application 29 days later. We also simulated these
203 alternatives in a scenario where only the first application of Met52 was performed.

204 *Metrics for the percent reduction.* In these different scenarios, we calculated the percent reduction
205 of the predicted (simulated) nymphal peak, i.e., the percent reduction in the number of feeding
206 nymphs per host at the peak of each nymphal season associated with each single treatment and
207 ITM approaches. We also calculated the percentage change in the area under the phenology curve,
208 which accounts for the seasonal variation in the densities of feeding nymphs compared to reference
209 plots, for simulated single treatments and combined efforts.

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Results

212 *Model calibration.* For all reference properties (ITM Reference), simulation outputs of the process-
213 based model yielded a BE value of 29.1%, a RMSE value of 1.12, a Pbias value of -64.9, and a
214 NSE value of -0.98, when the model was forced with near-surface air temperature weather station
215 data. Predictions of the calibrated model are shown in Figures 2 and S2. In the absence of
216 interventions, the model predicted yearly feeding nymphal peaks at around 3 nymphs per mouse
217 (Figures 2 and S2).

218 *Efficacy of interventions on the reduction of the peak in feeding nymphs.* The point estimate for f_M
219 was 1.25, meaning that the Met52 treatment was estimated to multiply the daily mortality of
220 questing nymphs and adults by 2.25 on the first day of application, an effect then decreasing with
221 time (equation 1). The point estimate for f_F was 4.11, meaning that the FipBox treatment was
222 estimated to multiply the daily mortality of feeding larvae and nymph by 5.11 on the first day, an
223 effect then decreasing with time (equation 2) (Figure S1). The point estimate for f_D was 0.985,
224 meaning that the Deer intervention was estimated to reduce by 98.5% the host-finding rate for
225 adults in yards. In model simulations utilizing these parameters, the efficacy of all interventions

226 was higher and was persisting for a longer time (Figures 3, 4 and S3) when they were applied for
227 a higher number of consecutive years. Combinations of multiple interventions were always more
228 efficacious than single interventions (Figure 3).

229 Among single interventions implemented for only one year, the “FipBox Only” intervention was
230 the most efficacious as it decreased the feeding nymphal peak on that year by 53.6% compared to
231 the “no intervention” scenario (by killing the nymphs feeding on hosts), versus 6.4% and 4.7% for
232 the “Deer Only” and “Met52”, respectively (Figure 3). However, because the FipBox treatment
233 affects both larvae and nymphs on host, it showed its peak efficacy on the nymphal population the
234 year following the one year of intervention (56.7% reduction of the nymphal peak) (Figure 4).
235 Similarly, because of its effects on the adult tick population, the “Deer Only” intervention reached
236 its peak efficacy two years after the one year of intervention, with a 19.6% decrease in nymphal
237 peak that year (Figures 4 and S3).

238 When implemented for several years, “Deer Only” reached a similar efficacy than “FipBox Only”,
239 i.e. a 97.0% versus 94.3% reduction (respectively) of the nymphal peak on the last year of four
240 years of intervention, compared to the “no intervention” scenario. The “Met52 Only” treatment
241 was less efficacious even after four years of implementation (16.1% reduction) (Figures 3 and 4).

242 The combination of the three interventions (Deer+Met52+FipBox) was always the most
243 efficacious, leading to a decrease of the nymphal peak of 59.6% (after 1 year of implementation)
244 to 99.8% (after four years of implementation), compared to the “no intervention” scenario. But it
245 was closely followed by the Deer+FipBox intervention whose efficacy was never more than 1%
246 lower than the Deer+Met52+FipBox scenario. Assuming four consecutive years of
247 implementation, all interventions (single and combined) reached a reduction in the nymphal peak
248 of more than 94% compared to no intervention, except “Met52 Only” (Figures 3 and 4).

249 *Comparison of percent reduction metrics.* The results described above were qualitatively similar
250 when we considered the reduction in the area under the feeding nymphs phenology curve instead
251 of the height of the feeding nymphal peak (Figures S4 and S5).

252 *Changes in the timing of “Met52 Only” interventions.* From our model simulations, the application
253 of the Met52 treatment on May 19th followed by a second application 29 days later led to the
254 highest reduction of the nymphal peak that year (-5.85% compared to the “no intervention”

255 scenario) (Figure 5). However, applying the Met52 treatment only once in mid-June led to almost
256 similar results (-5.13% compared to the “no intervention” scenario) while reducing the amount of
257 input needed (Figure 5). The advantage of applying a second Met52 treatment was different when
258 measuring the area under the phenology curve (Figure S6), with a maximum effect size of -3.61%
259 for two treatments, instead of -1.98% for one treatment, compared to the “no intervention”
260 scenario.

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Discussion

263 We found that combined treatments were globally more efficacious than single treatments in
264 reducing the number of *I. scapularis* nymphs in residential yards. Among single treatments, our
265 results suggest that deer reduction (“Deer”) and fipronil-based small rodent bait boxes (“FipBox”)
266 were more efficacious than the broadcast area-application of the entomopathogenic soil-borne
267 fungus *Metarhizium anisopliae* (“Met52”). Because interventions targeted different tick life
268 stages, they impacted the nymphal tick outcome at different time lags, with an immediate effect of
269 Met52, an effect of FipBox reaching its maximum after a one-year lag, and deer reduction two
270 years after the intervention¹⁶. Globally, a higher number of subsequent years of (single or
271 combined) interventions led to a better efficacy. Most interventions (except “Met52 Only”)
272 reached a reduction in the feeding nymph peak of more than 94% compared to “no intervention”
273 scenario, when implemented for at least four years. Moreover, we found that the optimal date for
274 a single application of Met52 in Connecticut residential yards would be around mid-June.
275 Preceding this application by another application one month earlier (in mid-May) would only
276 slightly reduce the height of the feeding nymph peak (maximum exposure potential), but would
277 reduce by around half the area under the phenology curve across the whole season. The area under
278 the phenology curve is a better measure of human exposure risk because exposure to host-seeking
279 nymphs can occur throughout the period of nymphal activity.

280 Previous empirical studies investigated the effect of interventions on the density of host-seeking
281 nymphal ticks, tick burden on hosts or the prevalence of tick infection by various pathogens
282^{16,18,20,27,28,41–43}. Some published models also theoretically simulated the implementation of
283 interventions (vaccination) in a tick-host system^{44,45}. Our study combined both of these

284 approaches by using the data collected from field experiments to estimate intervention effect
285 parameters in a mechanistic model. This method is innovative for tick-hosts systems, while more
286 common for other vector-borne disease systems⁴⁶⁻⁴⁸, and has several advantages. First, it provides
287 a mechanistic and dynamic understanding of interventions, in contrast with empirical-only studies
288 which only assess differences in a global output (e.g., the density of questing nymphs at a single
289 point in time). For example, we estimated that Met52 in our study multiplied the daily mortality
290 rate of questing nymphs and adults by 2.25 on the first day of application, and could estimate the
291 cumulative impact of the intervention during multiple years. Second, once mechanistic
292 intervention effect parameters are correctly calibrated to the data, it is possible to explore a wide
293 range of simulated treatment scenarios, in terms of timing or combinations of interventions.
294 Simulations are hence easier than implementing a large number of treatment options in the field,
295 and can narrow down which combinations, intensity and timing of interventions should be further
296 tested in experimental studies.

297 The effect sizes identified in our model were consistent with some previous studies. On the year
298 of intervention, we predicted similar reductions of the number of feeding nymphs per mouse
299 (nymphal burden) than a previously published empirical study⁴⁹ for both FipBox (around 50%)
300 and Met52 (less than 15%, not significant in the empirical study). Our results were also consistent
301 with Ostfeld et al.⁴² who found a stronger effect of FipBox than Met52 on the nymphal burden on
302 mice. If the complete removal of deer from a geographic area seems to effectively decrease nymph
303 abundance, the effect may be less clear for partial deer population reductions^{20,50}. In our study,
304 despite the fact the deer population was not entirely removed²⁸, we predicted a strong effect of
305 this intervention on the nymphal peak when it was implemented for several years. However, our
306 modeling framework did not include the infection process, and the effect of deer reduction on
307 nymph infection prevalence and the density of infected nymphs is still unclear^{50,51}.

308 In the future, expanding the model to include infection dynamics and other sets of interventions,
309 including vaccines and reductions in tick habitat suitability through landscape and vegetation
310 management, will allow estimates of efficacy in reducing the density of infected nymphs.
311 Integrating the costs of interventions would allow a more thorough cost-effectiveness analysis of
312 *I. scapularis* targeting interventions in residential yards⁵². Moreover, adding host behavioral

313 components to the model would more directly describe human exposure to tick-borne disease
314 hazard.

315

316

Conclusions

317 Computer simulations allow us to identify optimal control targets to minimize exposure to tick
318 bites and the risk for tick-borne diseases. Our goal is to provide information to stakeholders on the
319 optimal deployment of individual and combined tick management approaches, which can
320 synergistically contribute to short- to long-term, cost-effective and sustainable control of tick-
321 borne diseases in integrated vector management guidelines.

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Figures

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505 **Figure 1.** Sketch diagram of the modeling platform. Blue underlines highlight the endogenous
 506 variables of the Ogden et al. (2005) process-based model that are affected by weather conditions:
 507 time delay for the pre-eclosion period of eggs (q), host-finding probability for questing larvae,
 508 questing nymphs, and questing adults (λ_{QL} , λ_{QN} , and λ_{QA} , respectively), temperature-variable
 509 factors for questing activity of immature ticks and adult ticks (θ_i and θ_a , respectively), time delay
 510 for engorged larva to nymph development -or premolt period of engorged larvae- (s), time delay
 511 for engorged nymph to adult development -or premolt period of engorged nymphs- (v), and time
 512 delay for the pre-oviposition period (x). The orange, red and green arrows point to the exogenous
 513 and endogenous variables that are affected by the three single interventions (see main text): white-
 514 tailed deer population reduction (Deer), broadcast area-application of the entomopathogenic
 515 fungus *Metarhizium anisopliae* (Met52), and fipronil-based small rodent bait boxes (FipBox),
 516 respectively. A full description of all the parameters of the process-based model is included in the
 517 Supplementary material (level variables in Table S2; parameters in Tables S3 and S4; and discrete
 518 equations in Table S5).

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521

522 **Figure 2.** Daily time series of feeding ticks on host simulated by the dynamic tick population
 523 model for the historical period 2013-2019, for *in-situ* conditions corrected to reflect temperature
 524 and moisture conditions under leaf-litter, for weather-dependent host finding probability, and for
 525 the group of houses included in ITM Reference. Black and red time series depict the simulation
 526 outputs when the model is forced with near-surface air temperature weather station data. The blue
 527 dots depict the average number of observed densities of nymphs per 100 m².

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532 **Figure 3.** Percent reduction of the height of the feeding nymphal peak on the last year of
533 intervention, compared to the “no intervention” scenario. For each intervention (single and
534 combined), different alternatives for the number of years of implementation (from one to four
535 years) are presented. D: “Deer Only”; M: “Met52 Only”; F: “FipBox Only”; D+M: “Deer+Met52;
536 D+F: “Deer+FipBox”; M+F: “Met52+FipBox”; D+M+F: “Deer+Met52+FipBox”.

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547 **Figure 4.** Evolution of the percent reduction of the height of the feeding nymphs annual peak for
 548 each intervention, compared to the “no intervention” scenario. In our model simulations,
 549 interventions are all implemented in 2013, for one to four years. For each intervention and number
 550 of years, the dot represents the last year of intervention, with the line representing changes in effect
 551 size with years after the intervention ended. D: “Deer Only”; M: “Met52 Only”; F: “FipBox Only”;
 552 D+M: “Deer+Met52; D+F: “Deer+FipBox”; M+F: “Met52+FipBox”; D+M+F:
 553 “Deer+Met52+FipBox”.

555

556 **Figure 5.** Percent reduction of the height of the feeding nymphal peak in the only year of
 557 intervention, compared to the “no intervention” scenario, for different variations of the
 558 “Met52Only” treatment. One or two Met52 applications are simulated, starting at different dates
 559 between April 21st and July 14th. If done, the second Met52 application always takes place 29 days
 560 after the first one. The application of Met52 after the nymphal peak (here, after July 7th) has
 561 logically no impact on peak height.

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Supplementary material

569 Single “Deer Only” treatments were conducted in eight (8) houses. A single “FipBox Only” was
 570 deployed in one (1) house. A combination of Met52+FipBox was conducted in thirteen (13)
 571 houses, but in 2016 only FipBox were deployed. A combination of Deer+Met52+FipBox was
 572 conducted in five (5) houses, but in 2016 a combination of Deer+FipBox was conducted. A
 573 combination of Deer+FipBox was conducted in two (2) houses. Lastly, twelve (12) houses were
 574 used as experimental reference (i.e., controls) and received no intervention (Integrated Tick
 575 Management – ITM Reference).

576

577 **Table S1.** Assigned treatments to residential households (n=41) over four years as part of an
 578 integrated tick management program conducted in Redding.

#	Assigned treatment	2013	2014	2015	2016
1	Deer Only	Yes	Yes	Yes	\$, £
2	Deer Only	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
3	Deer Only	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
4	Deer Only	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
5	Deer Only	Yes	Yes	Yes	\$
6	Deer Only	X	Yes	Yes	Yes
7	Deer Only	X	Yes	Yes	\$
8	Deer Only	X	Yes	Yes	\$
9	ITM Reference	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

10	ITM Reference	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
11	ITM Reference	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
12	ITM Reference	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
13	ITM Reference	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
14	ITM Reference	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
15	ITM Reference	X	Yes	Yes	Yes
16	ITM Reference	X	Yes	Yes	Yes
17	ITM Reference	X	Yes	Yes	Yes
18	ITM Reference	X	Yes	Yes	Yes
19	ITM Reference	X	Yes	Yes	Yes
20	ITM Reference	X	Yes	Yes	Yes
21	Met52+FipBox and FipBox Only	Yes	Yes	Yes	FipBox Only
22	Met52+FipBox and FipBox Only	Yes	Yes	Yes	\$, £
23	Met52+FipBox and FipBox Only	Yes	Yes	Yes	FipBox Only
24	Met52+FipBox and FipBox Only	Yes	Yes	Yes	FipBox Only
25	FipBox Only	\$	\$	\$	Yes

26	Met52+FipBox and FipBox Only	Yes	Yes	Yes	FipBox Only
27	Met52+FipBox and FipBox Only	Yes	Yes	Yes	FipBox Only
28	Met52+FipBox and FipBox Only	X	Yes	Yes	FipBox Only
29	Met52+FipBox and FipBox Only	X	Yes	Yes	FipBox Only
30	Met52+FipBox and FipBox Only	X	Yes	Yes	FipBox Only
31	Met52+FipBox and FipBox Only	X	Yes	Yes	FipBox Only
32	Met52+FipBox and FipBox Only	X	Yes	Yes	FipBox Only
33	Met52+FipBox and FipBox Only	X	Yes	Yes	FipBox Only
34	Met52+FipBox and FipBox Only	X	Yes	Yes	FipBox Only
35	Deer+Met52+FipBox (Everything)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Deer+FipBox
36	Deer+Met52+FipBox (Everything)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Deer+FipBox
37	Deer+Met52+FipBox (Everything)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Deer+FipBox

38	Deer+FipBox	Yes	Yes	Yes	\$
39	Deer+FipBox	Yes	Yes	Yes	\$
40	Deer+Met52+FipBox (Everything)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Deer+FipBox
41	Deer+Met52+FipBox (Everything)	X	Yes	Yes	Deer+FipBox

579 Deer: White-tailed deer reduction; FipBox: Fipronil-based small rodent bait boxes; Met52:

580 Broadcast area-application of the entomopathogenic fungus *Metarhizium anisopliae*; ITM

581 Reference: Integrated Tick Management Reference.

582 \$ Not sampled; £ Withdrew

583

584 **Table S2.** Level or state variables of the Ogden et al. (2005) process-based, mechanistic model.

Life stage	Activity	Description
Eggs	--	Number of eggs, $Eg(t)$; $Eg(0) = 0$
Larvae	Hardening	Number of hardening larvae, $H_L(t)$; $H_L(0) = 0$ This level variable comprises hatched larvae undergoing a 21 day 'hardening' prior to becoming questing larvae.
	Questing	Number of questing larvae, $Q_L(t)$; $Q_L(0) = 0$
	Feeding	Number of feeding larvae, $F_L(t)$; $F_L(0) = 0$
	Engorging	Number of engorged larvae, $E_L(t)$; $E_L(0) = 0$
Nymphs	Questing	Number of questing nymphs, $Q_N(t)$; $Q_N(0) = 0$
	Feeding	Number of feeding nymphs, $F_N(t)$; $F_N(0) = 0$
	Engorging	Number of engorged nymphs, $E_N(t)$; $E_N(0) = 0$
Adults	Questing	Number of questing adults, $Q_A(t)$; $Q_A(0) = 10,000$
	Feeding	Number of feeding adult females, $F_A(t)$; $F_A(0) = 0$
	Engorging	Number of engorged adult females, $E_A(t)$; $E_A(0) = 0$
	Egg-laying	Number of egg-laying adult females, $EL_A(t)$; $EL_A(0) = 0$

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587 **Table S3.** Eggs- and larvae-related parameters of the Ogden et al. (2005) process-based,
 588 mechanistic model.

Life stage	Description
Eggs-related	Per-capita egg production by egg-laying females (p). Note: in the original version of the model, the maximum number of eggs produced by each engorged adult female was set to 3,000, following the suggestions by (Mount et al.,1997). In our revised version, p was set to 350 eggs.
	Daily, per-capita mortality rate of eggs (μ_E). Set to 0.0020.
Larvae-related	Time delay for hardening of larvae (z). Set to 23 days.
	Time delay for the feeding period of larvae (r). Ticks feed for a fixed time delay, after which they instantaneously <i>drop off</i> the host as engorged ticks. Set to 3 days.
	Daily, per-capita mortality rate of hardening larvae (μ_{HL}). Set to 0.0060.
	Daily, per-capita mortality rate of questing larvae (μ_{QL}). Set to 0.0060.
	Daily, per-capita mortality rate of engorged larvae (μ_{EL}). Set to 0.0030.

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591 **Table S4.** Nymphs-, adults- and hosts-related parameters of the Ogden et al. (2005) process-based,
 592 mechanistic model.

Life stage	Description
Nymphs-related	Time delay for the feeding period of nymphs (u). Set to 5 days.
	Daily, per-capita mortality rate of questing nymphs (μ_{QN}). Note: two approaches are proposed here: (i) set μ_{QN} to a constant value of 0.0060; or (ii) make the parameter dependent on the survival rate of questing nymphs, which is influenced by ambient conditions.
	Daily, per-capita mortality rate of engorged nymphs (μ_{EN}). Set to 0.0020.
Adults-related	Time delay for the feeding period of adult females (w). Set to 10 days.
	Time delay for oviposition (y). Set to a fixed time delay of 1 day, but it varies with temperature in nature.
	Daily, per-capita mortality rate of questing adults (μ_{QA}). Set to 0.0060.
	Daily, per-capita mortality rate of engorged adults (μ_{EA}). Set to 0.0001.
White-footed mice-related	Number of rodents (Rod) (hosts for immature ticks). Set to 250 rodents.
White-tailed deer-related	Number of deer (D) (hosts for adult ticks). Set to 20 deer.

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Level variable	Dynamic equation
Eg(t)	$\frac{dEg(t)}{dt} = EL_A(t) \cdot f_{FA}(t) \cdot p - \mu_E \cdot Eg(t) - \frac{Eg(t)}{q(t)}$
H _L (t)	$\frac{dH_L(t)}{dt} = \frac{Eg(t)}{q(t)} - \mu_{HL} \cdot H_L(t) - \frac{H_L(t)}{z}$
Q _L (t)	$\frac{dQ_L(t)}{dt} = \frac{H_L(t)}{z} - \mu_{QL} \cdot Q_L(t) - \lambda_{QL} \cdot Q_L(t) \cdot \theta_i(t)$
F _L (t)	$\frac{dF_L(t)}{dt} = \lambda_{QL} \cdot Q_L(t) \cdot \theta_i(t) - \mu_{FL}(t) \cdot F_L(t) - \frac{F_L(t)}{r}$
E _L (t)	$\frac{dE_L(t)}{dt} = \frac{F_L(t)}{r} - \mu_{EL} \cdot E_L(t) - \frac{E_L(t)}{s(t)}$
Q _N (t)	$\frac{dQ_N(t)}{dt} = \frac{E_L(t)}{s(t)} - \mu_{QN} \cdot Q_N(t) - \lambda_{QN} \cdot Q_N(t) \cdot \theta_i(t)$
F _N (t)	$\frac{dF_N(t)}{dt} = \lambda_{QN} \cdot Q_N(t) \cdot \theta_i(t) - \mu_{FN}(t) \cdot F_N(t) - \frac{F_N(t)}{u}$
E _N (t)	$\frac{dE_N(t)}{dt} = \frac{F_N(t)}{u} - \mu_{EN} \cdot E_N(t) - \frac{E_N(t)}{v(t)}$
Q _A (t)	$\frac{dQ_A(t)}{dt} = \frac{E_N(t)}{v(t)} - \mu_{QA} \cdot Q_A(t) - \lambda_{QA} \cdot \frac{Q_A(t)}{2} \cdot \theta_a(t)$
F _A (t)	$\frac{dF_A(t)}{dt} = \lambda_{QA} \cdot \frac{Q_A(t)}{2} \cdot \theta_a(t) - \mu_{FA}(t) \cdot F_A(t) - \frac{F_A(t)}{w}$
E _A (t)	$\frac{dE_A(t)}{dt} = \frac{F_A(t)}{w} - \mu_{EA} \cdot E_A(t) - \frac{E_A(t)}{x(t)}$

$EL_A(t)$	$\frac{dEL_A(t)}{dt} = \frac{E_A(t)}{x(t)} - \frac{EL_A(t)}{y}$
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598 *Supplementary Note 1.*

599 *Weather.* We downloaded the NOAA NCEP CPC GHCN CAMS (Fan and van den Dool, 2004;
600 2008) and UCSB CHIRTS v1.0 (Funk et al., 2019) gridded near-surface air temperature datasets
601 from the IRI Data Library. The first dataset is available at a spatial resolution of 0.5° and at a
602 monthly timescale for the continuous period spanning from January, 1948 to present. The CHIRTS
603 dataset is available at a spatial resolution of 0.05° and at a daily timescale, and its historical period
604 spans from January 1, 1983 to December 31, 2016. These datasets were restricted to the geo-
605 domain 40.47 to 41.53 N, and 74.58 to 71.81 W; i.e., a bounding box in the vicinity of Redding,
606 but the single gridpoint where the town is located was processed. The CAMS and CHIRTS datasets
607 were averaged to have a continuous daily time series of mean temperatures for the historical period
608 January 1, 1950 to present. For weather station data we used the set of daily observations gathered
609 at the station USW00054734 Danbury Municipal Airport, which is located at 41.37215°N,
610 73.48337°W and 138 masl. Records were downloaded from the Climate Data Online portal
611 (<https://www.ncdc.noaa.gov/cdo-web/>) of the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration's
612 National Centers for Environmental Information (daily summaries are available at:
613 <https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/maps/daily-summaries/>). The instrumental period of this weather
614 station spans from May 11, 1998 to present. We downloaded specific humidity data (at 1,000 mb)
615 from the publicly available 0.75°-arc global atmospheric ERA-5 reanalysis data of the European
616 Center for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts - ECMWF (Potter et al., 2018). To calculate
617 saturation deficit, specific humidity records were combined with sea level pressure and near-
618 surface air temperature data. ERA-5 datasets are available for the historical period spanning from
619 January 1, 1979 to August 31, 2019. The geo-domain of interest was also restricted to 40.47 to
620 41.53 N, and 74.58 to 71.81 W. Lastly, we calculated the daily day length of Redding using the
621 sunrise and sunset times available on the Global Radiation Group portal of the NOAA Global
622 Monitoring Laboratory at (<https://gml.noaa.gov/grad/solcalc>).

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626 **Figure S1.** Upper panel: Simulated increase (multiplicative factor depending on f_F (equation 2))
 627 in the daily per-capita mortality rate of feeding larvae (μ_{FL}) and nymphs (μ_{FN}), with the use of
 628 fipronil-based small rodent bait boxes (the FipBox intervention) during 4 consecutive years (2013
 629 to 2016) in the model. Boxes are assumed to be implemented in early May each year and again 8
 630 weeks later. Parameter f_F was estimated using data from residential properties. Lower panel:
 631 Number of feeding nymphs per mouse predicted by the model between 2013 and 2019, in the “No
 632 intervention” scenario *versus* in the scenario with fipronil boxes implemented for 4 consecutive
 633 years (2013 to 2016).

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637 **Figure S2.** 2013, 2014, 2015 and 2016 density of questing nymphs per 100 m² (DON) in the
 638 properties that were used as experimental reference and received no intervention (dots) along with
 639 the number of feeding nymphs per mouse simulated by the dynamic tick population model for the
 640 same years (lines).

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651 **Figure S3.** Number of feeding larvae, nymphs and adults per host predicted by the model between
652 2013 and 2019, in different examples of scenarios: “1yr_D”, “1yr_M” and “1yr_F” depict the
653 implementation of the “Deer Only”, “Met52 Only” and “FipBox Only” interventions, respectively,
654 for one year in 2013. “3yr_D”, “3yr_M” and “3yr_F” depict their implementation for three years,
655 between 2013 and 2015.

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668 **Figure S4.** Percent reduction of the area under the phenology curve (for feeding nymphs) in the
 669 last year of intervention, compared to the “no intervention” scenario. For each intervention (single
 670 and combined), different alternatives for the number of years of implementation (from one to four
 671 years) are presented. D: “Deer Only”; M: ”Met52 Only”; F: “FipBox Only”; D+M: “Deer+Met52;
 672 D+F: “Deer+FipBox”; M+F: “Met52+FipBox”; D+M+F: “Deer+Met52+FipBox”.

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675 **Figure S5.** Evolution of the percent reduction of the area under the phenology curve (for feeding
 676 nymphs) for each intervention, compared to the “no intervention” scenario. In our model
 677 simulations, interventions are all implemented in 2013, for one to four years. For each intervention
 678 and number of years, the dot represents the last year of intervention. D: “Deer Only”; M: ”Met52
 679 Only”; F: “FipBox Only”; D+M: “Deer+Met52; D+F: “Deer+FipBox”; M+F: “Met52+FipBox”;
 680 D+M+F: “Deer+Met52+FipBox”.

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684 **Figure S6.** Percent reduction of the area under the phenology curve (for feeding nymphs) in the
 685 only year of intervention, compared to the “no intervention” scenario, for different variations of
 686 the “Met52 Only” treatment. One or two Met52 applications are simulated, starting at different
 687 dates between April 21st and July 14th. If done, the second Met52 application always takes place
 688 29 days after the first one.

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